

Soil amendments in plant disease control

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The use of nonedible oil cakes and other agricultural and industrial by-products as important tools in biological control of plant pathogens has been recently recognized. Soil amendments encourage growth and multiplication of soil microflora and thus kill pathogens in soil by competition or antibiosis.

A field experiment at RRS in Moncompu during the 1978–79 punja (Oct–Jan) season studied the effect of various nonedible oil cakes and other by-products on the intensity of sheath

blight and sheath rot disease of rice.

The intensity of both diseases was lower in amended plots than in unamended plots. The results indicate that the oil cakes and other organic materials tested were equally efficient in suppressing sheath blight and sheath rot (see table). The benefit may be due to stimulation of soil saprophytes leading to a reduction in the pathogen population or to better plant tolerance because of increased nutrition offered by the amendment.

Oil cakes are also useful as insect and rodent repellent and as nitrogen inhibitor. Amending the soil with nonedible cakes will be a good practice in rice cultivation. ■

not only the fungal pathogen, but also by a *Trichoderma* sp. When sterilized rice straw was mixed with the *Trichoderma* and the sheath blight pathogen, the straw decomposed fast when mixed with *Trichoderma* alone. Speed of decomposition was lower with *Trichoderma* plus sheath blight pathogen, and slowest with the sheath blight pathogen alone. In a mixture, a large number of dead sclerotial bodies of *T. cucumeris* were recovered, and the mycelium was found coiled with the *Trichoderma* mycelium. ■

Effects of treatment with various by-products on the intensity of sheath blight and sheath rot. Kerala, India.

Treatments	Disease score ^a (0-9)	
	Sheath blight	Sheath rot
Neem cake (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>), 1 t/ha	2.33	1.93
Marotti cake (<i>Hydrocarpus</i> sp.), 1 t/ha	2.33	2.33
Rubber seed cake (<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>), 1 t/ha	2.73	2.46
Puma cake (<i>Callophyllum inophyllum</i>), 1 t/ha	2.86	2.06
Coconut pith (<i>Cocos nucifera</i>), 2 t/ha	2.46	2.60
Sawdust, 2 t/ha	3.40	3.00
Rice husk (<i>Oryza sativa</i>), 2 t/ha	2.86	2.73
Untreated control	7.26	7.00
C.D. (0.05)	1.67	1.72

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice scales. Sheath blight: 1 = lesions limited to lower 1/4 of leaf sheaths. 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves. Sheath rot: 1 = less than 1% [of tillers affected] (= to resistant check). 9 = 50-100% (= no susceptible check).

Ecology of the rice sheath blight pathogen: saprophytic survival

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It has been well established that the sclerotial bodies of the rice sheath blight pathogen *Thanatephorus cucumeris* serve as the primary inoculum source for initial infection. In temperate regions these sclerotia, usually numbering 1,000/m², overwinter in the soil after the rice harvest. An initial attempt at IRRI, a tropical region, indicated that in a field of more than 50% infection, only a small number of sclerotia could be recovered. Previous results indicated that many of the sclerotia in the

field were colonized by bacteria, many of which were antagonistic to the fungus.

The saprophytic survival of the pathogen was therefore studied by burying healthy rice straw pieces (2–3 cm apart from the internode) in unsterilized soil of dryland origin. The soil was mixed with different amounts of inoculum and incubated for 1 month under conditions of submergence, and 100% and 50% moisture saturation. The percentage of rice straw colonization by the fungus was lower under submergence than in 50% saturation. When infected rice straw pieces were buried in soil of dryland origin, recovery of the fungus was lower in unsterilized than in sterilized soil. In unsterilized soil and at 50% moisture saturation, a high percentage of the straw was colonized by

Reaction of wetland rice to dirty panicle disease and the influence of soil type and fertilization

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Dirty panicle disease of rice is becoming a major disease in Nigeria with the introduction of improved varieties and high-input technology. The disease has been observed on rainfed dryland rice, but incidence is higher on rainfed wetland rice. Although the precise extent of damage is not known, national rice pathologists associate the disease with a loss in quality of parboiled-milled rice because of the black grains.

In the 1979 wet season (Jun–Oct), the disease was widespread in trials at the Badeggi Rice Research Station and in neighboring rainfed wetland rice farmers' fields. A cooperative investigation was initiated on an acid Oxisol (Agaie soil series) to evaluate the performance of 5 recommended rice cultivars with 12 fertilizer treatments (see table) when exposed to dirty panicle disease under rainfed wetland conditions. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings of each cultivar were transplanted in a 30- × 36-m plot divided into 12 equal parts, 6 × 3 m each. The cultivars were scored for dirty panicle disease incidence during the grain-maturing stage.

IR8 and FARO15 (IR8/BG79) were least infected, suggesting varietal resistance. IR20 and SML140-10 were moderately susceptible, and MAS2401